

VERBAL CATEGORY OF VOICE AND ITS EXPRESSING IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract. The category of voice, is a verbal category which characterizes different relations between subject and object and is realized in endings of verbs. In Modern English there are two grammatical voices: the active voice and the passive voice. For that purpose, the aim of the research is to define the voice and analyze types of voice category. According to the result of the research, voice as a grammatical category incorporates semantic syntactic relations between the subject and the object of action.

Keywords: grammar, verb, category, voice category, active voice, passive voice.

There is no widely recognized definition of the category of voice in contemporary linguistics. R. Quirk asserts that "voice is a grammatical category that allows you to consider an action in a sentence in two different ways without any changes in the facts presented" [4, 64-122].

According to B.A. Ilish, "the voice expresses the nature of the relationship between the subject and the predicate, as well as the attitude of the action toward the object, if there is one in the sentence" [2, 54-56].

According to E.I. Korolev, "forms of voice express the same relationship between subject and object, but for each form of voice, subject and object are expressed by different parts of sentences" [3].

If we define the voice structure in terms of semantic-syntactic definition, then the nature of the relations in it is reflected through the functional interaction of different parts of speech in a sentence as well as by identifying the semantic meaning of the units.

In light of this, A. I. Moiseev makes the case that different voice forms convey various attitudes of the verbal action's subject and subject to the subject and object. In addition to being determined at the morphological level, the distinctiveness of the voice and other grammatical categories is also influenced by the ways in which they are expressed in terms of syntax and vocabulary [5]. Additionally, the varying degrees of grammatization of various means of expressing values impact the complexity of the voice. The English voice also has a few distinctive characteristics.

Both active and passive structures are present in every language. In all temporary forms, passive structures are utilized a lot in English. Linguists continue to wonder about both their quantitative and qualitative characteristics. Diachronic analysis makes it feasible to comprehend the theoretical basis for English language passive constructions and how they have evolved.

As a result, grammatical changes to the voice structure take place both at the sentence level and at the level of the verb phrase. The past tense participle of the main verb and the appropriate form of the auxiliary verb are added to the verb phrase to create the passive structure. The passive voice develops at the sentence level as a result of rearranging the sentence's constituent parts: the active subject becomes a passive agent, and the active object becomes a passive subject.

The active voice and the passive voice are the two grammatical voices used in modern English. The active voice indicates that the action is being done by the subject and is being directed at the object. When an action is directed at a subject rather than away from it, the passive voice

is employed to demonstrate this. The subject itself does not perform an action; rather, it is performed upon. The passive voice is not just an active voice parallel composition. The doer of an activity is frequently absent from passive structures. This is due to the fact that sometimes we are unaware of the person who committed an act, we are uninterested in it, or we just do not want to bring it up.

For example: This folk song was composed many years ago.

This machine is operated by hand, (we are not interested by whom the action is done, we are interested in the fact that the machine is operated by hand).

The teacher asked the pupil.

The teacher was asked by the pupil.

The only word that differs in the second sentence's second clause is the verb's voice. While the activity in the second sentence is directed toward the subject, it is directed from the subject to the object in the first sentence. As a result, the voice type indicates whether an action is directed away from or toward the topic.

Conclusion. We defined the voice as a grammatical category that incorporates semantic syntactic relations between the subject and the object of action after studying the theoretical aspect of the voice construction and various approaches to its description. The English language system's voice constructions incorporate the active voice in its morphologically initial form and vary from one another in how they combine morphologically derived forms. The passive voice, which indicates that the verb-predicate action is directed towards the person or thing conveyed by the subject, and the reflexive voice are alternatives to the active voice in modern English.

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